

CITY LIFE IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH CULTURE

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Abstract. Nowadays, urbanization of the mega cities is increasing rapidly which is making city life more hectic and live. However, city life is differs from country to country. In this article the researcher focuses on how city life in Uzbekistan and England looks like.

Keywords. Coherent traditions, Cosmopolitan familiarity, daily life and social customs, art of the culture, vibrant nightlife, pollution and adulteration, mixed culture, job chances and opportunities, Middle ages, Gissar mountains, Sarts fermers.

Cities nowadays are juggling two different existences. They serve as hubs for the arts, sciences, economy, and culture and draw the cutting edge of thought. However, influxes of newcomers are taxing infrastructure in cities all around the world. Many people question if cities are failing not only their residents but also the ecosystem as a whole because of their propensity to use tremendous amounts of resources.

One of the most powerful impressions of Uzbekistan, the main reason for its originality is its own urban culture of Greater Iran, that is so different from urban cultures of both Europe and Russia. And that urban culture in old Central Asian cities is centred around Mahalla.

Unlike neighboring Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan is historically an agricultural country. Of course, there had been Sarts farmers and nomadic Uzbeks with their 92 tribes, but in the twentieth century the nomad way of life practically stopped, and if the Kazakhs and Kirghiz learned to live settled in

Russian way, the Uzbeks learnt from the former Sarts with whom they merged into one nation. . Although 2/3 of the country is occupied by deserts and steppes, most of the Uzbeks live in huge oases, and watching typical rural settlement you will see green fields with farmers, big houses with wide darwaza (gates) in the shadow of pyramidal poplars, aryks (irrigation ditches) with spinning chigir (water mill) and brightly dressed women looking after countless children.

Even the name of the settlements often reflects its history: aul in the original meaning is a nomad yurt camp, whilst kishlak is an agricultural village, and therefore auls in Central Asia are usually faceless and with no character, whilst kishlaks are extremely colorful and full of life.

The most colorful villages, which have not changed much since the Middle Ages you will find in Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions on the slopes of Gissar mountains. And you can literally feel the history here not just in adobe houses with tall duvals (walls), but also in people living here. On the other hand, the 70 years under Soviet Union also transformed the life of Uzbeks, especially in towns and cities where people much differ from people in rural regions [1].

The traditions reflecting the multinational nature of Uzbekistan are present in its music, dance, painting, applied arts, language, cuisine, and clothing. Each region of Uzbekistan has its own unique shades as well, which are most clearly manifested in national dress and local dialects. To get acquainted with such richness and diversity, you must travel around the whole country, but the festivals of Uzbekistan are great events for those who want to see the whole palette of culture in this country in one place. [2]

10 Lines on City Life in English

City life is fast-paced and busy, with a constant hustle and bustle of people and activity.

Cities offer a diverse range of cultural and entertainment options, such as museums, theatres, and restaurants.

Cities are also centres of economic activity, with many job opportunities available.

However, city living can also be expensive, with high costs for housing and other necessities.

Cities tend to be more densely populated, leading to issues such as traffic congestion and air pollution [3]. Historically, English daily life and customs were markedly different in urban and rural areas. Indeed, much of English literature and popular culture has explored the tension between town and country and between farm and factory. Today, even though the English are among the world's most cosmopolitan and well-traveled people, ties to the rural past remain strong. Urbanites, for example, commonly retire to villages and country cottages, and even the smallest urban dwelling is likely to have a garden [4].

When it's talked more about English people's city life and the history of it we can actually catch that England was way homogenous country even centuries ago. It has a large diverse contributions from dozens of people like Afro-Caribbians, Asian, Muslims, Christians and so on.

All in all, each region of Uzbekistan has its own unique shades as well, which are most clearly manifested in national dress and local dialects. To get acquainted with such richness and diversity, you must travel around the whole country, but the festivals of Uzbekistan are great events for those who want to see the whole palette of culture in this country in one place.

Reference.

1. KODIROVA, H. (2023). INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA SOXTA DISKURSNING PRAGMATIK PARAMETRLARI. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 29(29). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/8920
2. KODIROVA, H. (2023). "MAVJUD PRAGMATIK KOMMUNIKATSIYA NAZARIYALARIDA "ALDOV/YOLG'ON" NUTQIY AKTLARNING NAMOYON BO'LISHI". ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ

(buxdu.Uz),

29(29).

извлечено

от

https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/8919

3. KODIROVA, H. (2022). РЕЧЬ АКТ АНАЛИЗ ТЕЛЕГРАММНЫХ СООБЩЕНИЙ О КОРОНАВИРУСЕ: СОЦИАЛЬНЫЕ СЕТИ И ФЕЙКОВЫЕ НОВОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 8(8). извлечено от

https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/5986

4. KODIROVA, H. (2022). Факторы возникновения ложных дискурсивных актов в устной речи. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 8(8). извлечено от

https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/5985

5. Kodirova Kholida Khayriddin kizi. (2022). The Analysis of Illocutionary Acts in Adventures of Tom Sawyer by Mark Twain. Miasto Przyszłości, 28, 324–328. Retrieved from

<http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/648>

6. Kodirova, H. K., & Norova, D. (2022). THE ROLE OF THE BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHING ESP STUDENTS. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON LEARNING AND TEACHING, 1(9), 235–238. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php/iclt/article/view/1882>

7. Nargiza Bobojonova Jumaniyozovna. (2022). Categorization in Modern Linguistics. Miasto Przyszłości, 28, 351–356. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/653>

Internet resources

1. https://uzbek-travel.com/about-uzbekistan/facts/uzbek_mahalla/
2. <https://www.rocapply.com/study-in-uzbekistan/about-uzbekistan/uzbekistan-lifestyle-and-culture.html>
3. <https://learners.com/10-lines-on-city-life-in-english/>
4. <https://www.britannica.com/place/England/The-arts>
5. <https://www.toppr.com/guides/essays/essay-city-life-vs-village-life/>

6. <https://www.timeout.com/uk/city-life>

7. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327127216_City_life_and_community